

EXPERIENCES IN RESULT-BASED PERFORMANCE MANAGEMENT SYSTEM OF SECONDARY SCHOOL TEACHERS

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ABSTRACT

The principal objective of this research is to determine the challenges educators face when compiling the Result-Based Performance Management System (RPMS) for the final report of the academic year, which incorporates teacher performance for the entire year. A phenomenological research design was utilized to gather the experiences of educators in Kulaman Districts, Sultan Kudarat Division, regarding the compilation of performance verification methods. In-person, semi-structured interviews were used to collect significant responses, which were analyzed using Colizzi's approach. It was evident that even with the challenges encountered by the educators in gathering reliable verification methods for each Key Result Area, they successfully produced significant portfolios that adhered to the Department of Education's criteria.

Keywords: *Teachers' Dilemma, Result-Based Management System (RPMS), IPCR*

INTRODUCTION

Teachers assume an indispensable function in enhancing the quality of instruction and knowledge acquisition. Effective teachers are crucial to increasing student achievement. Therefore, improving the skill level of educators is a primary focus of numerous educational reform initiatives aimed at guaranteeing high-quality education.

The Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (PPST) have been formulated and validated nationally to supplement teacher quality reform initiatives. Secretary Maria Leonor Briones of the Department of Education (DepEd) ratified this into policy via DepEd Order No. 42, section 2017. The PPST defines teacher quality by employing indicators, domains, and strands that effectively assess professional development, proficient teaching, and productive involvement

throughout a teacher's career. This document functions as a public declaration of professional responsibility that may assist educators in evaluating and analyzing their approaches to pursue individual advancement and expertise. As a follow-up to Civil Service Commission Memorandum Circular No. 06, s. 2012, or the Strategic Performance Management System (SPMS), the Department of Education issued Order No.2, s. 2015 — "Guidelines on the Establishment and Implementation of the Results-based Performance Management System (RPMS) in the Department of Education"—in 2015. This order aims to ensure that personnel perform in a practical, timely, and high-quality manner. The guidelines define the framework, standards, and procedure governing the establishment, oversight, assessment, and formulation of performance objectives.

The DepEd ensures that work efforts are focused on attaining its vision, mission, values, and strategic priorities to provide Filipino learners with high-quality educational services via the RPMS. In addition, instructors in the field have posted negative comments on social media regarding the preparation of verification means for the various observable objectives to achieve a highly satisfactory or even exceptional performance. There have been reports of several teachers whose suicidal acts were precipitated by classroom observation and other performance-related materials. Considering this, some teachers asked the department to discontinue the implementation of the new performance indicators for teachers, arguing that they may also be biased toward teachers who work minimally to earn high ratings.

Consequently, this study was designed to address this concern. In addition, the purpose of this research was not to reveal the negative impacts of this new performance standard on educators; rather, it was intended to generate a theme concerning the difficulties elementary school teachers in Kulaman I District encounter.

Research Questions

Relative to the preponderance of existing empirical studies about teacher performance, this study aims to answer the following research questions.

1. What are the struggles they have encountered in the preparation of means of verification of their performance?
2. How do teachers cope with the challenges they have faced in preparing means of verification for their performance?

METHODOLOGY

This investigation employed a phenomenological research design as it can study people's experiences, how people construct meaning in their lives, and commonalities that transverse individuals experiencing a specific phenomenon (Edmonds & Kennedy, 2017). Notably, this study utilized Transcendental phenomenology, which aimed to seek understanding in human experience, which is performed by laying aside prepossessed ideas to view the phenomena to be investigated through a new lens, allowing it to immerge, giving its distinct meaning and form (Moustakas, 2004).

The focus participants of this investigation are four (4) proficient teachers with a plantilla position of Teacher 1-3 and three (3) highly experienced teachers with a plantilla position of Master Teacher 1- 4, who were selected through purposive sampling. This phenomenological study

selected seven (7) participants that fit the suggestion of Creswell (2014) as an ample number of participants to generate meaningful themes and valuable interpretations.

RESULTS

The results were grounded in 4 major themes: **(a) Time Constraint, (b) Prioritization, (c) Intermediate Planning, and (d) Systematization**. The following themes are represented with sample significant statements (S.S.) from the five participants (P). The major themes were combined to synthesize the structure of the phenomenon.

DISCUSSION

Struggles encountered in the preparation of the means of verification of their performance

The Department of Education conducted training on selected teachers from each district during the third quarter. The purpose of the training was to introduce new guidelines for evaluating teachers' performance. These guidelines require teachers to identify valid means of verification (MOVs) for each Key Result Area (KRA), which consists of five major areas. Collecting valid means of verification is considered a crucial task for teachers, as they shared during the training.

"It is just about collecting data. However, honestly, that was my struggle" [P1, T1, F][SS5].

"First and foremost, I must know the documents to be attached per objectives, to identify the valid and invalid MOVs per domain and objectives and the reproduction or photocopy of the same MOVs for different objectives. Time constraint is also one of my struggles." [P6, MT1, F][SS6]

The way to achieve in public activity is through robust and productive work, which is conceivable by appropriately managing time. The modest era energizes individuals from as right on time as their primary education to plan and oversee time successfully. To achieve the set goals and perform better, time management and its utilization according to needs is required (Alay & Kocak, 2003).

Handling struggles in preparing the means of verification

Prioritization is arranging items or activities according to their relative importance. Efficiently manage your time and prioritize data collecting at the beginning of the academic year. Analyze the required papers based on the objective and the approved techniques for verifying your performance. Integrate all necessary tasks, as they have conveyed:

"To handle those struggles smoothly. I have to review the documents to be attached per objective and the valid MOVs for each in the PPST-RPMS manual. Pay personally for the reproduction of the same documents needed as MOVs for different objectives. Time management is necessary for preparing my MOVs." [P6, MT1, F][SS12] "Maximize your time, make/set as your priority" [P4, T3, M][SS10]

David Allen (2016) discourages the practice of prioritization, as he argues that priorities tend to fluctuate during the day. On the other hand, Stephen Covey (2017) promotes using the ABC

prioritization method to ensure that the most crucial tasks are completed first. Covey emphasizes the necessity of re-prioritizing the list when circumstances fluctuate. The conventional method for ranking a list is the ABC system. This technique utilizes a letter to designate the significance or immediacy of each job in your list. "A" represents the utmost significance or the highest level of urgency. Prioritize the tasks labeled as "A" by completing them first or today. Designate the letter "B" to denote items or tasks of lesser significance or lower priority. Allocate the letter "C" to items or tasks of lesser significance or urgency.

Dinkel (2012) also stated, "Prioritization can only be achieved after the organization process has been completed." There is no singular method for organizing, but the system you use must be logical and comprehensible to you. The organization's objective is to locate items efficiently without any time wastage.

Coping mechanisms on challenges faced in the compilation of the needed means of verification

In their scientific definition, psychologists Richard Lazarus and Susan Folkman (2017) describe coping as the combined cognitive and behavioral actions that individuals employ to manage specific challenges, whether they originate from within themselves or other sources and are perceived as burdensome or challenging. However, coping refers to the process of actively seeking and implementing solutions to stressful events or problems that arise as a result of our stressors. The term "coping" is primarily linked to "reactive coping" since it is commonly understood as a reaction to a stressor. Alternatively, a concept known as "proactive coping" involves employing coping strategies to avoid potential future stressors.

Although an individual's conscious mind is responsible for implementing coping mechanisms, not all result in favorable outcomes. Some coping mechanisms might be classified as maladaptive. According to other psychologists, maladaptive coping might be considered equivalent to "non-coping" because when a person employs a coping mechanism to deal with a stressor but fails to overcome or resolve the stressful circumstance effectively, they have essentially not coped with the stress at all, as reported by the participants.

"I should have a plan already. I set the details that I could gather every month. So no more struggling stuff during the deadline" [P5, T1, F] [SS15].

"Gradual preparation of MOVs, I tend to memorize all the details of the MOVc so that the next time, it is easy for me to find MOVs" [P2, T11, M] [SS13]

"Embrace and love changes in the department. Work with co-teachers and read and understand the RPMS manual" [P4, T3, M] [SS16].

"Patience, dedication, and I have to devote my time in the preparation of MOVs for my IPCRF," [P6, MT1, F,] [SS18]

Lessons learned on the compilation of the means of verification for your performance

Documenting and retaining the knowledge gained from any endeavor is crucial. The leader should firmly promote this approach from the very beginning. We acquire knowledge from project failures and accomplishments, which we can then apply to current projects for better preparation or to discover areas for improvement in project management processes. Otherwise, we are destined to reencounter comparable circumstances. According to Rowe, S. F. & Sikes, S. (2006), we need to maximize project successes to take advantage of opportunities to establish effective methods

and practices for completing current and future work. The participants of the study also expressed this sentiment.

"I have to focus my time on the compilation of my IPCRF, the necessary valid MOVs, label it with different domains and objectives, and put it in an envelope as early as the school year so that when the time comes to prepare my IPCRF documents there were already intact," [P6, MT1, F] [SS24].

"Do not wait for tomorrow. What can you do today, sorting things in order and providing portfolio or folder for the MOVs to be inserted", [P1, T1, F] [SS19]

"I learned that it is easy to provide MOVs if you properly document all your activities related to IPCRF. I learned that this served as a checklist if you performed your basic tasks as a teacher well for the whole year round [P2, T2, M] [SS20].

In addition, as Idowu Koyenikan (2017) stated, "There are certain life lessons that you can only learn in the struggle.". Furthermore, according to the Project Management Institute (PMI) Project Management Body of Knowledge (PMBOK), lessons learned refer to the knowledge acquired via the execution of a project. Lessons learned sessions are often done formally and are traditionally scheduled towards the end of a project, during its close-out phase.

Nevertheless, it is possible to identify and capture lessons learned at any stage of the project's life cycle. The objective of documenting lessons learned is to disseminate and utilize the knowledge acquired from past experiences to facilitate favorable results and mitigate the repetition of unfavorable outcomes. Lessons learned encompass the procedures required for recognizing, documenting, validating, and sharing lessons learned. The utilization and integration of these processes involve identifying relevant lessons learned, documenting them, archiving them, distributing them to the appropriate personnel, identifying actions to be taken based on the lessons learned, and conducting follow-up to ensure that the appropriate actions have been implemented.

Conclusions

As a result of the challenges encountered during the development of the means of performance verification, the subsequent themes and concepts emerged: "Time Constraint." They must prepare valid and essential documents affixed to each critical result area in various objectives.

On the other hand, a theme of prioritization was developed to address challenges encountered during the preparation of verification means. Consequently, instructors can organize and manage materials or tasks according to their significance to the goals specified in the critical outcome domains.

The theme of intermediate planning was centered on mitigating mechanisms for the difficulties encountered while compiling the necessary verification means. Therefore, they must devise a strategy to gather valid substantiation methods for each objective.

The theme of systematization emerged from the insights gained regarding the compilation of valid means of verification for performance, which indicates the criticality of such compilations across crucial result areas.

Recommendations

Based on the key findings of this study, the following recommendations were made: quarterly preparation of valid means of verification and a review of the various objectives in each key result area by educators to compile the means of verification in a meaningful manner. Educators frequently consult the quarterly manual for preparation guidelines and consult with the rater or school administrators to organize the classroom observation tool's implementation as a valid means of verification. Instructors may devise a transitional strategy that functions as a navigational tool to effectively authenticate the legitimate verification methods employed by the school administrator or rater to adhere to the requirements of the Department of Education. Expanding the extent of research regarding implementing Commitment and Review Forms, Result-Based Management Systems, and individual performance could provide a more comprehensive and readable picture.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The interview process with the respondents has been carefully planned to highlight the principles of respect, confidentiality, and informed consent in compliance with the ethical standards that govern research. Prior to conducting the interviews, each participant was provided with a comprehensive explanation of the study's objectives, methodologies, and the voluntary nature of their involvement. During the informed consent process, participants were clarified that their participation was entirely voluntary and that they had the freedom to withdraw from the study at any point without incurring any penalties. Moreover, the study ensured careful adherence to participant confidentiality, ensuring that any disclosed information would be collected and anonymized. The formulation of interview questions was significantly shaped by ethical considerations, ensuring that the queries were respectful, nonintrusive, and focused on the objectives of the study. The interview procedure was conducted with utmost adherence to the highest ethical standards to ensure the protection of the rights and well-being of the participating teachers.

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